

$$[.CH_2CH(OH)C\bar{O}_2] = \frac{-(k_2k_6[H_2O] + k_1k_8) + \sqrt{(k_2k_6[H_2O] + k_1k_8)^2 + 8k_1k_4k_6k_8[\text{Malic acid}]}}{4k_6k_8} \quad \dots (10)$$

On neglecting the negative root, Equation (10) can be re-written as

$$[.CH_2CH(OH)C\bar{O}_2] = \frac{(k_2k_6[H_2O] + k_1k_8)}{4k_6k_8} \left\{ -1 + \left(1 + \frac{8k_1k_4k_6k_8}{(k_2k_6[H_2O] + k_1k_8)^2} [\text{Malic acid}] \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\} \quad \dots (11)$$

Since experiments are done at low malic acid concentrations and water is present in large excess, it can be assumed that

$$\frac{8k_1k_4k_6k_8 [\text{Malic acid}]}{(k_2k_6[H_2O] + k_1k_8)^2} \ll 1$$

Therefore equation (11) can be simplified as

$$[.CH_2CH(OH)C\bar{O}_2] = \frac{2k_1k_4 [\text{Malic acid}]}{(k_2k_6[H_2O] + k_1k_8)^2} \quad \dots (12)$$

On substituting the value of $[.CH_2CH(OH)C\bar{O}_2]$ from (12) in (9), we get

$$-\frac{d[S_2O_8^{2-}]}{dt} = k_1[S_2O_8^{2-}] + k^1[S_2O_8^{2-}] [\text{Malic acid}] \quad \dots (13)$$

Where k_1 is the first order rate constant for the thermal decomposition of peroxydisulphate in absence of any substance and k^1 is bimolecular rate constant for the oxidation reaction. Thus, equation (13) gives the same rate law as expected from the experimental results of Kumar and Saxena¹.

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Relation Between Lattice Energy and Melting Points of 3d Metal(II) Oxides

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In a family of closely related crystalline compounds where the same potential energy function is applicable on fusion, a direct proportionality between the lattice energy ($-U_o$) and absolute melting point^{1,2} (T_m) is expected. Since different members under this condition are in a similar state of mutual interaction, they usually conform to a general constancy of the ratio $-U_o/T_m$. This trend has been well-maintained for the oxides of s and f block metals^{1,2}, respectively. It was, therefore, thought meaningful to investigate the family of 3d metal(II) oxides from the above view point and compare the results of $-U_o/T_m$ ratios for s, d and f block metal oxides. The desired data of Born-Haber lattice energy⁴ and absolute melting points^{5,6} for the oxides of present interest were taken from literature and the values of $-U_o/T_m$, thus calculated, are recorded in Table I.

Regression analysis :

Excluding the ratio of $-U_o/T_m$ for FeO as recorded in Table I (the reason being given under

TABLE I—RELATION BETWEEN $-U_o$ and T_m OF 3d METAL(II) OXIDES

Metal oxides*	$-U_o$ (k cal mole ⁻¹)	T_m (K)	$-U_o/T_m$ (k cal mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
TiO	949	2023	0.47
VO	947	ign.	—
MnO	929	1923	0.48
FeO	954	1693	0.56**
CoO	978	2073	0.47
NiO	995	2263	0.44
CuO	1004	1999 dec.	—
ZnO	985	2243	0.44

* $-U_o$ and T_m data for SnO and CrO are not available in literature.

** Significant trend.

Results and Discussion), the proposed relation for other members of the family have been subjected to regression analysis. Assuming a linear relation between $-U_o$ and T_m , one can write :

$$T_m = a + bU_o \quad \dots (1)$$

Using the criteria of least squares and solving the normal equations, one obtains the final form of eqn. (1) as :

$$T_m = 4.99U_o - 2721.33 \quad \dots (2)$$

Thus, the regression coefficient (b) of the concerned relation is 4.99 with its estimated standard error equal to ± 1.07 . Moreover, the correlation

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coefficient (r) between the two variables $-U_o$ and T_m is 0.94 to indicate a very satisfactory linear relationship.

Results and Discussion

As is clear from Table 1, the values of $-U_o/T_m$ for different 3d metal(II) oxides appear to show a general close agreement with each other. The ratio observed in case of Fe(II)O, however, has a significant trend and needs an explanation. $-U_o/T_m \approx 0.56$, obtained therein, may either be due to higher lattice energy, $-U_o$, or lower melting point T_m . Since $-U_o$ used is derived from a reliable Born-Haber procedure⁴, the T_m value of Fe(II)O should be of doubtful accuracy. Literature does reveal that pure sample of iron oxide with an exact 1:1 stoichiometry is not known in actual practice^{7,8} to support the assumption made earlier.

Out of the oxides included in Table 1, Fe(II)O is reported to be devoid of true equilibrium and an attempt to produce it results in disproportionation to α -iron and ferrous oxide richer in oxygen content⁹. It is probably due to this fact that the properties of non-stoichiometric phase of ferrous oxide do change remarkably⁹ as compared to its expected 1:1 ideal stoichiometric phase. The vitiated ratio of $-U_o/T_m$, obtained for FeO, is thus quite clear. Ferrous oxide possesses a nearly constant composition of Fe_{0.95}O instead of FeO over a high temperature range of 900-1300 K, whereas for other companion oxides viz., Ni(II)O, Co(II)O and Zn(II)O, the departures from normal stoichiometry of 1:1 is relatively much insignificant^{10,11} even upto 1273 K. In Zn(II)O, for example, deviation from normal stoichiometry of the excess of zinc over oxygen is only $7 \times 10^{-3}\%$. It may thus be safely concluded that contrary to Fe(II)O, the other oxides of the family appear to show no net non-stoichiometry upto their melting points to observe a well behaved average constancy of $-U_o/T_m \approx 0.46$.

The maximum and minimum deviations of the average ratio are within 5%, except for FeO. A correspondence of lattice energy at the absolute melting points is thus satisfactorily established conforming to a general relation given by $-U_o/T_m \approx 0.46$. For the reason given earlier, one would disregard FeO as a regular member of the family for which the anomalous $-U_o/T_m$ value of 0.56, being about 22% higher than the average $-U_o/T_m \approx 0.46$, is perhaps a direct evidence to it. Using the relation, $-U_o/T_m \approx 0.46$, in conjunction with $-U_o^\ddagger$ of Fe(II)O tends to predict the ideal melting point of a conceptually synthesised sample of this oxide to be 2073 K which is meaningfully higher than the experimental T_m value⁶ of 1693 K. This is what one should demand from a well-known defective stoichiometry of FeO. Similarly, on assuming the principle of similarity, the hypothetical melting points of V(II)O and Cu(II)O should be around 2060 and 2180 K, respectively. The T_m data, thus predicted, are in fair agreement with those obtained from eqn. (2).

Further, it is interesting to compare the observed numerical values of $-U_o/T_m$ in s, d and f block metal-oxides. The overall mean values of $-U_o/T_m$ for the oxides of alkaline earths¹ (s² metals), 3d metal(II) oxides and 4f metal(III) oxides⁸ are 0.30, 0.46 and 1.23, respectively. The successive involvement of metals coupled with s, d and f orbital characteristics among the oxides of three categories tend to increase the $-U_o/T_m$ ratios in a very significant manner. A similar trend is followed by s and d block metals as well, whose respective $-U_o/T_m$ values^{1,2} are 0.41 and 0.66.

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Studies on Azo Derivatives of 1-Hydroxyanthracene

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WE report here the synthesis and spectral properties of eight new azo derivatives of 1-hydroxyanthracene.

Synthesis of 1-hydroxyanthracene: It was prepared by sulphonation of anthraquinone in presence

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